

UCHQIR-PITNAK SHAFT OF CHORJOI STAGE TO CARRY OUT SEARCH AND PERFECT SEARCH WORKS USING BUKHARA DIMENSIONAL (3D) TOTAL DEPTH POINT (UCHN) METHOD

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Purpose of work.

Conducting exploration and perfect exploration of the UQFRZ located between the Uchqir-Pitnak valley, Burgutli and Tuzkoy depressions of the Bukhara and Chorjoi ridges using the 3D (3D) common deep point (UChN) method, and the construction of previously and newly identified structures. Determination of oil production in the Russian and Jurassic layers and preparation for deep steaming.

Administrative work was carried out: Bukhara region, Karakol district

Tectonic aspect: Uchqir-Pitnak valley, Burgutli and Tuzkoy depressions of Bukhara and Chorjoi ridge.

Methodology of work:

31) during the seismic survey, a 720-channel telemetry system was used to record seismic data through the US-made INPUT/OUTPUT «I/O IMAGE SYSTEM – MRX» station.

The receiving (LP) and the driving (LV) lines are mainly designed and developed in a regular network. The number of consecutive landings was 45.

An orthogonal symmetric 3D tracking system with 540 active channels was used in 5 LP. In this case, the number of MRX channels is 324, and RSR channels are 216. The step between LP is 500 m., and LV is 300 m., and the distance between PP and PV is 50 m. Seismic wave excitation was performed using a group of 2 SVs at a 50m base. Parameters of the sweep signal (cone-0.5 s threshold frequencies -

10-80 Hz., recording time - 12s., (sweep signal length - 8s) number of exposures - 16. Two group I I seismic receivers were used every 2.5 m on the basis of 52.5 m.

Topographic and geodetic works.

The coordinates and elevations of P V and PP were determined using a GPS satellite positioning system, and the Pelton-GPS system was used to determine the coordinates of the actual position of SV.

Volumes of topographic and geodetic works performed in November 2021: determination of PV and PP coordinates and heights using the GPS system at 50 m intervals: Uchqir s/p 31) according to the Ng 09/2018-2021 project; 3930 k.t. or 196.45 pog.km.

Information about recording equipment:

During the 3D seismic survey, a 720-channel telemetry system was used to record seismic data through the US-made INPUT/OUTPUT «I/O IMAGE SYSTEM – MRX» station. Tests of field equipment have also shown that they work correctly. In general, the operation of the seismic complex is checked online by the manufacturer's built-in diagnostic programs. The correct operation of GPS satellite positioning systems has been verified through a network of national triangulation points.

The standard passport of the seismogram provided by the IMAGE image system contains enough initial information for the user. A conversion was performed to obtain a seismogram with similar multiplication parameters to the MRX field seismogram. If necessary, seismograms were sorted by PV and PP.

Field material processing and seismic data quality analysis were performed at the Field Seismic Data Processing Center using 3D MESA software.

Field materials are sent to PGMP "Uzbekgeofizika" JSC every month.

Works performed by Uzqir s/p 3D 09/2018-2021 seismo search party

Uzqir s/p 3D X209/2018-2021 project, 42 templates according to JNè2 block addition.

Number LP 6, 7, 8, 9, 10.

Number LV- 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35, 36, 37, 38,

39, 40, 41, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57.

LP- 6, between PP-PP 37-390, LP- 7, between PP-PP 37-390,

LP- 8, in the range PP-PP 37-390, LP- 9, in the range PP-PP 37-390, LP- 10, in the range PP-PP 37-390,

3D seismic survey party in November 2021

Under the Uchqir s/p 3d Ng 09/2018-2021 project, the following amount of work was completed on the N22 block addition: 4275 f.n or 75 kV in Shim.Parsankol area. km.

11. The quality of the obtained material was evaluated by rewriting the seismograms made during the field work. In general, the materials were rated satisfactorily. The quality coefficient of the received material

0.86.

The quality of the obtained material allows to solve the task after processing in EHM at the end.

Productive horizons can be observed anywhere between 2.2-2.5 s and 1.0-1.8 s gaeha.

12. Conclusions and recommendations:

In order to continuously perform field work, as well as to save fuel, the task of renewing the kos, kosichka and boxes was set. The geological-technical task for November 2021 was completed with a quality coefficient of 0.86.

Topographical and geodetic work on this INFORMATION

In November 2021, the ZD seismic research party performed topographical and geodetic works of the following size: N22 additional block section 1 in Shim.ParsankUI area. Determination of coordinates and heights of points with positioning system

<<GPS>> - 3930 k.t. or 196.45 pog.km.

The specified types and volumes of work were implemented on the basis of the main and additional projects of Uchkir d/p ZD 18-2021.

Time section along the profile Cr 6520

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